

THE ROLE OF UZBEK LITERARY CRITICS IN THE THEORY OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *This article focuses on the theory of translation and the role of Uzbek literary works in world literature. Information about the scientists who contributed to the translation and their research will also be passed. Scientists who contributed to the development of Uzbek literary traditions in the ranks of masterpieces of world literature are listed.*

Keywords: *International Association of Translators (FIT), English, German, French, Alisher Navoi, Babel, World Literature, Moscow.*

Translation enriches the spiritual life of a person, realizing the possibilities of his native language, making him colorful. Thanks to the translation, the research books are sharpened and enriched with new ideas and concepts. The first studies devoted to the theory of translation began to occur in 20-30 years of the last century. In the books of Amos, Postget, Finkel, Alekseev, published during this period, and in the treatise of Sanjar Siddiq “The art of translation of literature” (1936), we meet theses recognized as a science in the theory of translation. In the 50s, after the publication of articles by the well-known translator Ivan Kashkin and linguist Reformatzky about the theory of translation, discussions began in this area. Professor Reformatzky put forward the idea that “Although the practice of translation serves all disciplines, the theory of translation can not be an independent science, but can be a branch of linguistics.” After that, several studies, articles were published, which approved and criticized them. 1953-year The International Association of Translators (FIT) was founded. From 1955-year, his body began to publish the magazine “Babel” (Babel). Later, studies of world scientists devoted to the theory of translation and the problems of translation criticism were printed one by one. And this determined the prosperity of scientific research of scientists. By the 70s of the last century, an independent science was formed, which was called “transliteration” in the world of philological science. In the development of translation Science in Uzbekistan, such scientists as Jumaniyoz Sharipov, Ninel Vladimirova, Gaybulla Salomov, Najmiddin Komilov, Kudrat Musaev had great service. To date, the Uzbek School of translation has been recognized in the world science of

translation. Let's not look at the literary life of which developed country in the world, we see that classical examples of literature of other peoples are translated. Uzbekistan is also no exception in this matter. Thanks to the great skill of translating the tragedy "Hamlet" in 1935, the Uzbek translator managed to get the status of a magnificent art school. The first stage of Shekspir "Hamlet" on the Uzbek stage, what a great cultural event in our cultural life, the translation "Hamlet" from the golden pen of the Chulpan is such a great and unforgettable literary event in the history of Uzbek translation literature.[1]

Among these translators, it is worth emphasizing Alexander Faynberg, the owner of the Pushkin medal, a well-known scholar of literature, a researcher who took the leading places in the field of research of the works of Uzbek literary critics in World Literature, in my opinion. Alexander Faynberg is a great translator. He opened up the creativity of many Uzbek poets to Russian readers. In Moscow, the poem "Rebellion of Souls" by the people's poet of Uzbekistan- Erkin Vohidov, a collection of translations from the work of Uzbek poets named "The group of Swans" was published in Tashkent. Poems of the well-known poet turned to the Uzbek language in the book "Winch" reached the readers' hands. [2] People's poet of Uzbekistan, member of the Association of cinematography Alexander Faynberg was awarded the Pushkin medal for his worthy contribution to the cultural relations between Russia and Uzbekistan by the decree of the president of Russia (2009). The poet's work is fruitful and extensive. In his poems, colourfulness, philosophically, thoroughness, clarity of feelings is flared. The poet feels the word deeply, this feeling is also accompanied by the reader. He lived and worked in Uzbekistan. The air of this land, the sky, the soil, in a word, the whole existence is dear to the heart, up to the poet. It seems that at the temperature of the poet's lines, his works are all over the neck, the height of which strikes our breath. We feel that in the work of Alexander Faynberg there is a strong interest in the works of Alisher Navoi. Because it translates rare works and works created by Uzbek literary critics into the Russian language, thereby creating a special place in world literature. In particular, the ghazal of Alisher Navoi has not remained from the point of view of many poets and translators until now, standing in the ranks of masterpieces. In the collection of works published by Alisher Navoi translated by Faynberg. As a person with such honour, Faynberg always felt happy. It should be said that during the work of Faynberg studied the whole creation of Alisher Navoi. [3] Alisher Navoi ghazals were translated into Russian by many poets. "However, not all of the translations came out as a

disappointment. M. Derjavin, S. Ivanov and others are much more shallow and distant from the artistic point of view than Navoi's poetry, that is, from the original. The creativity of the poet is incredibly high than they thought. The most priceless and inseparable part of Faynberg's creativity is that he can understand the subtle and mysterious concepts that other translators, researchers have not been able to understand. He does not translate the work, he studies the origin of the work and its root essence.

In modern times, the practice of translation (regardless of the type of translation) is based on science. Of course, in the process of creativity, intuition does not have its role and dignity. Science opens the way for translation to come out full-fledged and reliable. Translation criticism is a kind of science that is becoming a part of the translation and its composition but has not yet fully manifested itself. This science cooperates firmly, connecting close communication with linguistics, linguistics, stylistics, semantics, semiotics, etc. We expect a lot of useful work, from translation criticism and translation criticism to creative practice. If the practice of translation develops on an equal footing with the theory of criticism, knowledge of translation, translation, we always dream that everyone takes a step. We are delighted with the performances that reflect the theoretical and educational articles, the quality and level of translations, how close or far they are to the original, the ethics of translation, or, most importantly, comparative (with the original and the language of translation compared) analysis, which are visible on the pages of the press of social media, we follow them with interest. Connoisseurs of translation, knowledgeable in many languages, aware of the theory, eagerly looking at and approaching this area — we look with hope that researchers contribute to the revitalization of the process, we wish that their range will not be sparse. In the field of science, how good it is that there are general laws, laws, criteria! After all, what does the analyst, the narrator rely on his criticism, opens the field, expand the field of studying language? Although the legalities and dimensions! It is also because of this that we are talking about the theory of translation and the need for scientific studies, manuals on criticism — the current state of translation criticism is not in demand. In the translated works presented by newspapers and magazines, editors are reaching the reader through whom they can: Do the editors who prepared them for publication know that the work is written foreign language or is it based only on their belief in the translator? Translated from English (German, French), are there editors who prepare the translation of printed works for publication in comparison with the original in literary publications, in publishing houses? [4]

The fact that the skilled editor's pencil has not touched, no matter how it turned, the number of translation works that are going out in this vein is increasing, of course, is alarming.

Conclusion: Translation serves to find new relationships, views in society. Translation positively affects the culture and spirituality of different peoples. The translation is a factor in the organization and improvement of communication. Translation accelerates the process of interrelation and interrelation of literature of different peoples. Thanks to the translation works, they will enjoy the masterpieces of world literature.

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